

A STUDY ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND FORMABILITY PERFORMANCE OF STRETCH-BROKEN CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Continuous carbon fiber (CCF) for forming the complex shape is limited due to the fiber's difficulty to conform to deep draws. The continuous carbon fiber composite is often results to surface wrinkling and fiber breakage. Therefore, this research aims to establish the alternative production method of continuous carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites by using textile technology to improve the mechanical properties and formability performance of complex shape product by using the commingled yarn of stretch-broken carbon fiber (SBCF) technique. Stretch-broken carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites are interesting for manufacturing composite parts in aeronautic and automobile industries. With these materials it is possible to produce composite parts with complex geometries, and high curvatures. The SBCF is performed by combine broken carbon fiber slivers and spun with thermoplastic filaments to form fine, commingled yarns. The commingled yarns are wrapped with a continuous serving filament of the same polymer to stabilize the yarn for subsequent weaving processes. After that these commingled yarns were fabricated into woven fabric. In this research the fabrics were compressed by using flat and complex mold. The effect of SBCF on mechanical properties and formability performance of the composites were evaluated. It was found that by increasing molding temperature, molding pressure and molding time, the mechanical properties of SBCF composites are increased. While formability performance of composites, the SBCF composite could be produce better shape than CCF.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the past the forming of thermoset carbon/epoxy composites (particularly pre-impregnated fabrics and unidirectional continuous sheets of material known as "prepregs") into complex double curvature parts has been a very time consuming and expensive proposition. The aircraft industry has been at the forefront of composites research and one can imagine that parts made from composites for that industry must be virtually defect free if used for structural purposes or as part of the wing or fuselage[1].

Thermoplastic composite materials have received much interest for structural applications over the last 40 years, particularly in the aerospace field [2]. Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites (CFRTP) have become widely applied in the aerospace and automotive industries. Moreover, high performance engineering thermoplastics have been increasingly combined with the continuous carbon fiber (CCF) reinforcements. CFRTP have various advantages such as high fracture toughness, recyclability as well as the possibility to re-melt and reprocess compared with thermo-setting composites. Therefore, the CFRTP is very interesting candidate for composites to deal with the global

environmental issue in which natural resources are used effectively. However, there are many problems for the development of CFRTP. One of those problems is that formability performance of CCF, it is well known that continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites are limited formability of complex shape. Forming continuous carbon fiber material into complex shape can result in undesired wrinkles and fiber breakage. While, discontinuous fiber could allow for a substantial improvement in the production of complex shapes part.

Interest in aligned discontinuous fiber materials has increased significantly in recent years as they facilitate new and more cost effective forming techniques for complex shaped composite parts compared to continuous fiber systems [3].

The Stretch-Broken carbon fiber (SBCF) material being discussed in this research is formulated from broken carbon fibers slivers and spun with thermoplastic filaments to form fine, commingled yarns. The commingled yarns are wrapped with a continuous serving filament of the same polymer to stabilize the yarn for subsequent weaving or braiding processes as shown in Fig.1. The benefit of SBCF materials in reducing manufacturing costs of select aerospace polymer matrix composites (PMC) demonstration components has been reported [4].

Fig.1 Schematic drawing of stretch-Broken carbon fiber (SBCF)

The purpose of this research is to study the effect of stretch-broken carbon fiber on mechanical properties and formability performance of the composites made with SBCF compared to CCF. The flat plate, square and hemisphere shape was produced from both material types. The effect of SBCF on mechanical properties and formability performance of the composites were evaluated.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials used in this research are commingled yarns and film stacking. The commingled yarns by using SBCF technique was manufactured by Schappe Techniques (France). The yarn is composed of nylon matrix and carbon reinforcement. The matrix is a polyamide 12. The reinforcement of the composite material is carbon fibre. These commingled yarns were fabrication into the woven by using weaving twill2/2 pattern.

While film stacking technique, the materials used in this process were carbon fiber plain woven fabric (T700SC-3K, Toray Co., Ltd.) as the reinforcement and polyamide 6 film (PA6 CM1006, Amilan, thickness: 100 μ m, Toray Co., Ltd.) as matrix resin.

- **Compression molding by using flat mold**

For SBCF composite, 8-ply of SBCF twill2/2 (0/90° or \pm 45°) woven fabric was dried in an oven set at 100°C for 3 hours prior to compression molding to produce composite plates. First condition, the woven fabrics were placed into a pre-heated molding at 100°C and compression molding by various molding temperature at 190, 200 and 220°C with a molding pressure of 3 and 10 MPa for 2, 5 and 10 minutes as shown in Fig.2. The second condition, the SBCF woven fabric 8 ply or 1 ply were placed into a pre-heated molding at 100°C and compression molding was performed at the optimum parameter from the first condition.

Fig.2 Compression molding of SBCF woven composites

For film stacking (FS) composites, 9 ply of PA6 films and 8 ply of carbon fiber or 2 ply of PA6 films and 1 ply of carbon fiber (0/90° or ±45°) plain woven fabrics was dried in an oven set at 100°C for 3 hours prior to compression molding to produce composite plates. The woven fabric and PA6 film were placed alternating into a pre-heated mold at 100°C and compression molding was performed at 250°C with a molding pressure of 10 MPa for 10 minutes as shown in Fig.3.

Fig.3 Compression molding of film stacking composites

Cooling was subsequently performed by running water through the mold while keeping the specimens under constant pressure.

- **Compression molding by using square mold**

A 450 kN H1F 45 mechanical servo press from by Komatsu Industries Co., Ltd. was used. The forming die is shown in Fig. 4. The CFRTP sheet such as SBCF and FS sheet were heated with an infrared heater at 250°C and 270°C, respectively and then CFRTP sheet were placed into the lower die by sheet holder. The temperature of the die is 80°C. The upper die moves down at a speed of about 16 mm/s and stops at the dead center of the lower die.

Fig.4 Compression molding by using square mold

- **Compression molding by using hemisphere mold**

For the process of CFRTP compression molding condition composites by using hemisphere mold as shown in Fig.5, the same parameter as the second condition of flat mold compression. Cooling was subsequently performed by running water through the mold while keeping the specimens under constant pressure.

Fig.5 Compression molding by using hemisphere mold

To study the formability of a complex shape made with SBCF/PA12 compared to CCF/PA6. The box and hemisphere shape was produced from both material types. These specimens were investigated using visual inspection.

• **Testing Method**

To observe the impregnation state of the composite, the cross-section of composites was embedded in epoxy resin and then polished in order to observe the fiber impregnation by inverted microscope ZEISS Axio Vert.A1.

For the mechanical property, 3-point bending test of composites was performed by using Shimadzu Autograph AG-X plus 5kN. The specimen size was 100mm in length, 15mm in width and 1.8~2.0 mm in thickness. The span length was 80 mm and the test speed was 5mm/min.

To evaluate and understand the behavior of composites, bias-extension test of 1 ply dry fabric and composites was performed by using Shimadzu Autograph AG-X plus 100kN with oven. The specimen size was 200 mm in length and 25 mm in width. The span length was 100 mm and the test speed was 50 mm/min.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

• **The optimum compression molding of SBCF composites**

Fig.6 Relationship between flexural properties and molding temperature of SBCF composites.

In Fig.6 shows the relationship between flexural properties and molding temperature of SBCF composites. The mechanical properties of SBCF composites were increased with increasing molding temperature, molding pressure and molding time.

190°C/ 3 MPa/ 2 min

220°C/ 10 MPa/ 10 min

Fig.7 Cross section observation of SBCF composites

In Fig.7 shows cross section observation of SBCF composites at low and high of molding temperature, molding pressure and molding time. The impregnation of composites was increased with increasing molding temperature, molding pressure and molding time because void as shown in black color could not be observed after increased those parameters.

From above results, the mechanical properties of composites increased because the impregnation of composites was increased. It can be said that, the optimum condition for SBCF composite is 220°C for molding temperature, 10 MPa for molding pressure and 10 min for molding time could be produce better mechanical properties.

- **Bias-extension test of dry woven fabric and composites**

Fig.8 (a) Bias-extension properties of dry woven fabric ($\theta = 45^\circ$) and (b) the behavior of dry woven fabric after test by various the temperature in the oven

In Fig.8 shows bias-extension properties and the behavior after test of dry woven fabric ($\theta = 45^\circ$) by various the temperature in the oven. At room temperature (RT), the force of SBCF was slightly different to CF fabric. While under temperature of SBCF fabric, force was decreased with increasing temperature in the oven. The shape of dry fabric specimens by under temperature, width of dry fabric has become narrow than room temperature specimen.

Fig.9 (a) Bias-extension properties of dry fabric ($\theta = 0/90^\circ$) and (b) the behavior of fabric after test by various the temperature of oven

In Fig.9 shows bias-extension properties and the behavior after test of dry woven fabric ($\theta = 0/90^\circ$) by various the temperature in the oven. At room temperature (RT), the force of SBCF was higher than CF $0/90^\circ$. While under temperature of SBCF fabric, force was decreased with increasing temperature in the oven same as dry fabric $\theta = 45^\circ$. The shape of dry woven fabric specimens by under temperature, width of dry woven fabrics are not changed too much but fiber become to misalignment.

Fig.10 (a) Bias-extension properties of composites ($\theta = 45^\circ$) and (b) the behavior of composites after test by various the temperature of oven

In Fig.10 shows bias-extension properties and the behavior of composites after test by various the temperature of oven ($\theta = 45^\circ$) by various the temperature in the oven. In this case the results are similar to dry fabric $\theta = 45^\circ$ results, at the room temperature force and shape of composites was decreased with increasing temperature in the oven.

Fig.11 (a) Bias-extension properties of composites ($\theta = 0/90^\circ$) and (b) the behavior of composites after test by various the temperature of oven

In Fig.11 shows bias-extension properties and the behavior after test of composites ($\theta = 0/90^\circ$) by various the temperature in the oven. These results are similar to dry fabric $\theta = 0/90^\circ$, at under temperature of SBCF fabric, force was decreased with increasing temperature in the oven. The shape of composite specimens by under temperature, the width of composite are not changed too much and fiber become to misalignment.

From above results, it is noted that the temperature have effect on the behavior of dry woven fabric and composites. Dry woven fabrics and composites could move well at higher temperatures.

- **Formability performance of composites**

- **Square shape molding**

SBCF (0/90°)/250°C/ Die temp 80°C

CCF (0/90°)/270°C/ Die temp 80°C

Fig.12 The formability performance of SBCF (0/90°) composites and CCF (0/90°) composites by using square shape molding at 80°C

In Fig.12 shows the formability performance of SBCF (0/90°) composites and CCF (0/90°) composites by using square shape molding at 80°C. From the front (F), left (L), right (R) and back (B) side of specimen, in the case of SBCF composites could be observed fiber splitting and some fiber misalignment at the edge of each side in specimen. While in the case of CCF composites could be observed fiber splitting, the fibers sliding contact each other at the edge of specimen and fiber

misalignment.

Fig.13 The formability performance of SBCF ($\pm 45^\circ$) composites and CCF ($\pm 45^\circ$) composites by using square shape molding at 80°C

In Fig.13 shows the formability performance of SBCF ($\pm 45^\circ$) composites and CCF ($\pm 45^\circ$) composites by using square shape molding at 80°C . In the case of SBCF composites could be observed small fiber splitting at the edge specimen. While in the case of CCF composites could be observed some fiber splitting at the edge and resin-rich region in some area in specimen.

From the above results, the formability performance of woven fabric $\pm 45^\circ$ composites could be produced square shape better than $0/90^\circ$ composites and SBCF composites could be produce square shape better than CCF composites.

- **Hemisphere shape molding**

1 process

2 process

Fig.14 The formability performance of SBCF composites by compression molding 1process and 2proces into hemisphere shape

In Fig.14 shows the formability performance of SBCF composites by compression molding 1process and 2proces into hemisphere shape. Both of 1process and 2proces could not be observed wrinkle line and resin rich region on the surface of specimens. While the impregnation of composites, it could be observed some void region in the composites.

Fig.15 The formability performance of CCF composites by compression molding 1process and 2proces into hemisphere shape

In Fig.15 shows the formability performance of CCF composites by compression molding 1process and 2proces into hemisphere shape. Both of 1 process and 2 process could be observed wrinkle line and resin rich region on the surface of specimens. While the impregnation state, many voids could be observed inside and around fiber bundle of composites.

From the above results, it can be said that the formability of SBCF composite by using hemisphere mold could be produced specimen better surface, impregnation and low void content than CCF composites for both process.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The mechanical properties of SBCF were increased with increasing molding temperature, time and pressure. It can be said that, the optimum condition for SBCF composite is 220°C for molding temp, 10 MPa for molding pressure and 10 min for molding time could produce composites with better impregnation and mechanical properties

The formability performance of composites by using square and hemisphere mold, in the case of square mold the woven fabric $\pm 45^\circ$ composites could be produced square shape better than 0/90° composites and SBCF composites could be produce square shape better than CCF composites. While, hemisphere mold SBCF composites could not be observed wrinkle line and rich-resin region on the surface of specimen. It can be said that, the formability performance of SBCF composite could be produce better shape than CCF.

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